

Niosomes as versatile nanocarriers: a review of recent application advances and challenges

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This review provides a critical summary of recent advances in the development and application of niosomes as versatile nanocarriers, emphasizing their potential in enhancing drug delivery, improving therapeutic efficacy, and enabling targeted treatment. This review also attempts to highlight the major challenges associated with the formulation and the clinical translation of niosomes, and discusses the future directions for their successful application in nanomedicine. Niosomes are vesicular drug delivery systems formed from non-ionic surfactants that have gained considerable attention as versatile and efficient carriers for modern therapeutics. Structurally, niosomes consist of a bilayer membrane similar to liposomes, but they are more stable and cost-effective due to the use of non-ionic surfactants instead of phospholipids. This bilayer architecture enables the simultaneous encapsulation of both hydrophilic drugs (within the aqueous core) and lipophilic drugs (within the bilayer), making niosomes highly adaptable for a wide range of pharmaceutical applications. One of the key advantages of niosomes over conventional drug delivery systems is their ability to improve the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic profiles of drugs, as they can (i) enhance drug stability by protecting the active compound(s) from degradation, (ii) prolong the drug circulation time in the bloodstream, and (iii) provide controlled or sustained drug release. Additionally, niosomes can increase drug bioavailability, reduce systemic drug toxicity, and even enable targeted or local-

ized drug delivery, which is particularly important for drugs with narrow therapeutic windows or significant side effects. To date, traditional methods of niosome preparation (such as the thin-film hydration and solvent-based techniques) have been widely used due to their simplicity and reproducibility. However, recent advancements have introduced more sophisticated and precise approaches. For example, the implementation of microfluidics allows for a better control over the vesicle size and uniformity, while the adoption of quality-by-design strategies can optimize formulation parameters in order to ensure consistent product quality. Furthermore, the use of surface functionalization has enabled the development of targeted niosomes by attaching to them ligands that recognize specific cells or tissues. Stimuli-responsive systems, which release drugs in response to environmental triggers such as pH, temperature, or enzymes, have further enhanced the therapeutic potential of niosomes. The integration of niosomes into gels or hybrid platforms has also expanded their applicability, particularly in topical and transdermal delivery. These technological advancements have significantly broadened the clinical applications of niosomes, and they are now being explored for oral, topical, transdermal, ocular, and intranasal drug delivery. Furthermore, niosomes exhibit great promise for use in anticancer therapies by improving drug targeting and reducing toxicity to healthy tissues. The niosome use in antimicrobial treatments and vaccine delivery systems

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is also being investigated, as they can enhance immune responses and improve the stability of antigens. Unfortunately, despite these promising developments, several challenges remain in translating niosomal formulations into clinical practice: issues related to large-scale production, batch-to-batch reproducibility, long-term stability, sterilization, and regulatory standardization still need to be addressed. Of these, ensuring consistent quality and efficacy of niosomes across different manufacturing scales is particularly critical for commercial viability. In conclusion, niosomes represent a highly versatile and rapidly evolving platform for drug delivery. Given the ongoing innovations in formulation design and manufacturing technologies, they hold significant potential to bridge the gap between experimental research and clinically effective therapies, ultimately being able to improve patient outcomes across a wide range of medical conditions.

Keywords

drug delivery; nanocarriers; niosomes; non-ionic surfactant; targeted therapy

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Conflicts of interest statement

None to declare.

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